

ISSUES OF LABOR EDUCATION IN THE SPIRITUAL DEVELOPMENT OF LEARNERS

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The most important method of physical and spiritual development of the individual is labor education. Both in public and traditional pedagogy, the term “labor training” is used, which meant various types of labor training of learners in general education schools. As a result of the political and economic crisis in our country, which also affected education, the subject "Labor Training" was transformed into the educational field "Technology".

"Technology" picks up the baton of labor training at a new stage in the development of education, does not deny what was tested at school earlier, and does not contradict it. “There is a fundamental difference between technological training and labor training: educational goal-setting in preparation for work is always aimed

at developing learners' abilities to perform labor actions in ideal conditions for the implementation of the technological process. However, the knowledge, skills and abilities that the learner received in the process of learning on the ideal model of the technological process often turn out to be incomparable with real production and life situations.

This approach means the need to comply with specific requirements for the content of technology training and its educational and methodological support: the formation of flexible, mobile knowledge, as well as the ability to creatively apply them in atypical situations. In order to realize the goals and objectives of technological training, it is necessary to expand the didactic material for

learners, reflect the environmental, historical and economic aspects of a particular area of technological training, offer a model for the practical activity of learners in a variety of conditions, and ensure the development of learners' creative activity "(V.P. Kazakevich).

In our work we will use the term "labor training", in the third chapter we will show the relationship between the historical and modern concepts, essence and content of the subject "Technology", since in the period we are studying and now the term "labor education and training" has been and will be used, which is inextricably linked with the subject "Technology".

Based on the foregoing, we analyzed the tasks, content, types and pedagogical conditions of labor training and education at the present stage, since they are directly related to the traditions and customs of the past.

If we talk about the tasks and contents of labor education, then the labor education of a child begins with the formation in the family and school of elementary ideas about labor duties.

Labor has been and remains a necessary and important means of developing the psyche and moral ideas of the individual. Labor activity should become a natural physical and intellectual need for learners. Labor education is closely connected with the polytechnic training of learners. Polytechnic education provides knowledge of the basics of modern engineering, technology and organization of production, equips learners with general labor knowledge and skills, develops a creative attitude to work, and contributes to the right choice of profession.

Thus, polytechnic education is the basis of labor education. In the conditions of a general education school, the following tasks of labor education of learners are solved: the formation of a positive attitude towards work, high social motives for labor activity; development of cognitive interest in knowledge, the desire to apply knowledge in practice, the development of the need for creative work; the formation of high moral qualities: diligence, duty and

responsibility, purposefulness and enterprise, efficiency and honesty; equipping students with a variety of labor skills and abilities, forming the foundations of a culture of mental and physical labor [2, p. 260].

The content basis of the labor education of schoolchildren is the following types of labor: educational, socially useful and productive.

The educational work of a schoolchild includes mental and physical labor. Mental labor is the most intense; it requires great willpower, patience, and perseverance. The habit of daily mental work is of great importance for all types of labor activity. Socially useful work is organized in the interests of the members of the entire team and each child individually. It includes self-service work at school and at home (cleaning the classroom, school territory, household work at home, caring for plantings), summer work in the fields during school holidays.

The productive work of students involves the participation of schoolchildren in the creation of

material values, during which they enter into production relations, learn the meaning of environmental concepts and categories [2, p. 260].

Professional orientation of schoolchildren. Career guidance is a substantiated system of socio-economic, psychological-pedagogical, medical-biological, industrial and technical measures aimed at helping learners and young people in professional self-determination.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev emphasized the need to: "... organize special "situational rooms" in district (city) employment centers, vocational training centers and vocational schools located at close range, develop electronic programs and visual aids for professional orientation of learners of educational institutions "[1]

A correctly chosen profession corresponds to the interests and inclinations of a person, is in complete harmony with recognition. In this case, the profession brings joy and satisfaction. The social significance of a profession increases if it meets the

modern needs of society, is prestigious, has a creative character, and is highly valued financially. The world of professions is very mobile. Some professions are fading, others are emerging. The number of professions is in the tens of thousands, and learners need versatile information about them, qualified advice at the stage of choosing a profession, support and assistance at the beginning of their professional development. This is how the problem of building a system of career guidance work with learners arises.

In the course of developing scientific, technical and social progress in Karakalpakstan, a new type of citizen-worker is being formed, characterized by democratic conviction, a harmonious combination of physical and mental labor, a broad professional and cultural outlook, skill, a deep knowledge of the foundations of educational activities, and a creative and conscious attitude to work. The reform of the education system, carried out in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, is based on the creative development

of the principles of a unified labor and polytechnic school and is aimed at raising the level of education, improving the preparation of schoolchildren for independent working life. The recent laws and resolutions adopted on questions of education, training and upbringing emphasize the enduring role and importance of the labor education of learners in the context of the restructuring of the entire education system.

These conceptual tasks urgently require further improvement of the system of labor education of learners as an integral part of general and vocational education, aimed at the formation of a comprehensively developed personality. In our particular case, the criterion for learners' readiness for professional activities, for the performance of social functions, are the systems of qualities developed in the course of the educational process and as a result of independent work, the skills for which were instilled in school years. The

initial type of work for the learner is educational work.

Therefore, much here depends on the formation of a positive attitude towards learning among learners. However, educational work in the process of educational work, occupying most of the time of learners,

has a huge impact on the formation of their moral and labor qualities, among which hard work occupies a leading place. Namely, this quality is the solution to all problems in the field of education. Therefore, each era in its own way tries to find effective methods of educating industriousness in young people.

REFERENCES

1. Выступление Президента Республики Узбекистан Ш.М.Мирзиёева на форуме молодёжи Узбекистана 26 декабря 2020 \\ Правда Востока. Yuz.uz
2. Юзликаева Э.Р., Мадьярова С.А., Янбарисова Э.Э., Морхова И.В. Теория и практика общей педагогики - Т., 2012. – 260 с.
3. Покутнев В.Н. Художественное творчество и народная культура. В ст. XXI век: духовно-нравственное и социальное здоровье человека - М., МГУКИ, 2001 - с.113.
4. Urazbayeva, R. D. (2015). Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” and the National Program for Personnel Training: implementation in the system of higher education. Scientific thought. (P.34-37). Moscow. № 1.
5. Republic of Uzbekistan: The birth of an independent state. – (1992). Tashkent: Uzbekistan (P. 9-11)
6. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2010) Tashkent: Uzbekistan. (P. 98).
7. Qaraqalpaqstan XIX a’sirdin’ ekinshi yarimidan XXI a’sirge shekem. (2003). Nukus: Qaraqalpaqstan. (P. 554).
8. Alimova, D. A. (2008) History as history, history as science. Tashkent: Uzbekistan. #1. (P. 164).

9. Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. (1993) Nukus: Qaraqalpaqstan Uzbekistan. (P. 87).
10. BA Kurbanovna. Trends in parliamentary effectiveness in ensuring the development of society. Восточно-европейский научный журнал, 33-36, 2020
11. BA Kurbanovna. Development And Role Of Representative Authority In The Development Of Society, Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching 2, 113-117, 2021
12. A Bayrieva. Ensuring Balance Among Branches of Public Power During the Development of Civil Society in Uzbekistan. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine 7 (2), 2233-2239, 2020
13. АК Байриева. Ўзбекистонда вакиллик ҳокимияти органлари ва фуқаролик жамияти институтлари ҳамкорлигининг сиёсий-ҳуқуқий масалалари. Международный журнал консенсус 1 (3), 2020
14. И.Б. Жоллыбекова. Международное сотрудничество средних и высших специальных учебных заведений Каракалпакстана в научно-технической сфере и в подготовке кадров. Вестник развития науки и образования, 67-70, 2012
15. И.Б. Жоллыбекова. Международные культурные связи и сотрудничество в области науки, техники и образования Республики Каракалпакстан. Научная жизнь, 93-95, 2011
16. И. Жоллыбекова. Сотрудничества республики каракалпакстан по вопросам охраны окружающей среды и здоровья людей. Вестник Каракалпакского Государственного университета имени Бердаха №1-2. 2013
17. И.Б. Жоллыбекова. Международные акты республики каракалпакстан по вопросам охраны здоровья людей. Zbiór raportów naukowych 32, 2014
18. И. Жоллыбекова. Қарақалпоқ давлат университетининг халқаро алоқаларининг ривожланиши. Вестник Каракалпакского Государственного университета имени Бердаха №12014

- 19.Р.Дж.Уразбаева, И.Б.Жоллыбекова. Закон республики узбекистан" об образовании" и национальная программа по подготовке кадров: осуществление в системе высшего образования. Научная мысль, 34-36, 2015
- 20.И.Б. Жоллыбекова, Т.А. Абуллаев. Пути развития международного сотрудничества в области популяризации национального культурного наследия в годы независимости Республики Узбекистан. Научная мысль, 62-64, 2015
- 21.I.B. Jolibekova. Development of international cultural relations of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. International Journal on Integrated Education 2 (5), 105-108, 2019
- 22.Z.I.Bakhytovna.Foreign cooperation of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the field of environmental protection. Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities 3, 58-60, 2021
- 23.J.I.Bakhytovna. Development of tourism in the republic of Karakalpakstan. *Academicia: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 11.10. 2021.
- 24.И.Б. Жоллыбекова. Роль международного сотрудничества в социально-экономическом развитии Республики Каракалпакстан (1991-2018 гг.). Каракалпакский Государственный Университет, 2020.
- 25.Z.I.Bakhytovna. Development of international cultural relations of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol 7 (7), 2019
- 26.И.Б.Жоллыбекова. Международные отношения республики каракалпакстан и развитие науки. Астраханские Петровские чтения, 47-49, 2020
- 27.JI Bakhytovna. Science in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY* 2 (3), 82-85, 2022
- 28.IB Jolibekova. Training of personel in the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the years of Independence. *Science and Education in Karakalpakstan* 2 (2), 104-108, 2019
- 29.IB Jolibekova. International Relations in the field of education in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. *Science and Education in Karakalpakstan* 2 (2), 93-99, 2018

- 30.ИБ Жоллыбекова. Вопросы оценки образования в современных условиях. Материалы международной научно-практической конференции 1 (2), 69-71, 2017
- 31.ИБ Jolibekova. Features of the development of International economic relations Republic of Karakalpakstan at the present stage. 1 International Conference on Sustainable Development and Economics 1 (1 ...), 2017)
- 32.ИБ Jolibekova. Peculiarities of development of international economic relations of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Europe Applied Science. Europaiche Fachhochshule 1 (1), 400-402, 2015
- 33.ИБ Жоллыбекова. International relations in the field of science. Technology and education of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Postepy w nauce w ostatnich iatach. Nowych rozwiazan. Сборник научных трудов ..., 2013
- 34.ИБ Жоллыбекова. Основы международных экономических отношений в законодательстве Каракалпакстана.
- 35.Вестник Национального Государственного Университета имени Мирзо Улугбек 1 (1 ...), 2011)
- 36.ИБ Жоллыбекова. Проблема Арала и международное образование. К 90- лет юбилею Национального Университета Узбекистана 1 (1), 42-47, 2008
- 37.ИБ Жоллыбекова. Изучение истории народного образование в Каракалпакстане. Вестник Академии наук Республики Узбекистан отделении Каракалпакстан 1 (4 ...), 2006)
- 38.ИБ Жоллыбекова. История подготовки медицинских кадров в Каракалпакстане. Вестник Академии наук Республики Узбекистан отделении Каракалпакстан 1 (3 ...), 2006)